

Extending the Cartography Classroom with LBS: the Design, Implementation, and Preliminary Evaluation of a Guided Tour Educational Module.

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Abstract. This paper describes the design and implementation of an educational module for an advanced cartography course, which tasked students with creating map-based guided tours delivered through a web browser. Web-enabled guided tours have been utilized in geographic curriculum to support situated learning—directly connecting theory with real-world locations—but this has rarely, if ever, extended to the cartography classroom. The goal of the module was twofold: create a tangible connection between the mapmaking process and place, and cultivate mobile-first and LBS design skills. To assess the module, I used a combination of quantitative and qualitative surveys, as well as an instructor’s log to record issues and insights.

Keywords. Pedagogy, Guided Tours, Mobile-First Design

1. Introduction

In this paper, I describe the design, implementation, and preliminary evaluation of an educational module used in an advanced cartography course at the University of Wisconsin—Madison. The *Guided Tour Module* tasked students with researching and designing their own web-enabled, map-based guided tours. The *Guided Tour Module* was designed to teach mobile mapping methods and foster critical thinking about the relationship between maps, the mapmaking process, and place.

In particular, the *Guided Tour Module* was built upon principles of **situated learning**, a pedagogical approach which connects students to the real-world context of course material (Lave and Wegner 1991). Maps have long been used to support situated learning in university classrooms, and in

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recent years have leveraged both mobile mapping and location-based services (Mountain 2011, France et al. 2021). Mobile mapping has been used in a variety of contexts within geographic education (Roth et al. 2018, Pánek and Glass 2018, Jarvis et al. 2016, Pánek et al. 2018). However, most applications are centered within human geography coursework, not cartography. By centering mobile mapping and situated learning within an advanced cartography course, I used the educational module to explore critical cartography concepts and foster web design skills.

2. The Guided *Tour Module*

2.1. Guided Tours

Guided tours are unique expressions of cartography, creating a direct connection between maps and places by guiding users through the landscape. Mobile devices, such as smartphones, allow for the delivery of guided tours through either dedicated applications or a web browser. Location-based services allow information to be related directly to a user's location.

2.2. Module Delivery

The *Guided Tour Module* was delivered in the Fall 2024 iteration of *Geography 572: Graphic Design in Cartography*, which enrolled 22 students. The *Guided Tour Module* was delivered over three weeks in November. Each student was tasked with researching and designing their own browser-based guided tour centered on a location around campus or their own neighborhood. Work and instruction on the technical implementation of the walking tours was done primarily in course lab sections. Lecture sections were divided between traditional lectures related to mobile mapping and place, and a research activity designed to help students brainstorm potential topics and locations.

2.3. The *Web Guided Tour Library*

Geography 572 centers basic web-design skills, introducing students to HTML and CSS. Most students enter *Geography 572* are encountering HTML/CSS for the first time. Because the course does not teach Javascript, and has no Javascript prerequisite, students needed to be able to design their guided tours using HTML and CSS alone.

I designed a basic HTML library—creating a template using Leaflet and Javascript—which students can then manipulate through HTML/CSS. The *Web Guided Tour Library* creates guided tours that are comprised of **stops** (points-of-interest) and a **route**. When a user reaches a stop, they tap a cir-

cle on the map, which opens a splash screen containing information about that stop (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: Demo template of the *Web Guided Tour* library. *Left:* Default tour view. Circles represent stops, the line represents the tour route. *Middle:* Individual stop view, accessed by tapping a stop circle. *Right:* Zoomed out view of tour route.

The library allows students to edit two data files, *stops.csv*, which contains information about stop locations and includes images and descriptions, and *route.geojson*, which specifies the route between each stop. From there, students can change the basemap in HTML, and customize the design using CSS.

3. Methods

3.1. Instructor’s Log

Throughout the implementation of the *Guided Tour Module*, I recorded reflections from lecture and lab sections. Instruction—especially when based in situated learning—rarely goes as planned. The log is a method to record curricular issues and technical bugs, as well as student successes, to reflect and learn from the teaching experience based on the actual implementation of curriculum in the classroom (Roth and Sack 2018).

3.2. Exit Survey

Following the submission of their Guided Tours, students were given the option to complete an optional survey for extra credit. The survey consisted of two sections. The first was a series of likert-style questions centering their experience with the module, while the second included a series of long-form reflection questions to gather qualitative feedback.

4. Preliminary Results

Through the instructor's log and survey responses from 15 students, several trends have emerged. In general, participants felt the creation of their tours improved both their technical skills and deepened their relationship to the setting of their tour. As one participant wrote: "It made me feel much more connected to the current and past people and non-people that exist on my tour route." On a technical level, 87% (n=13) noted some improved in their HTML skills after completing their tour, while 93% (n=14) noted improvement in their CSS skills. While students faced some minor technical issues, the library largely worked as expected, and no students experienced critical bugs.

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